

BUSINESS DEVELOPMENT BASED ON VOICE OF CUSTOMER SYSTEM TO IMPROVE SERVICE QUALITY IN CULINARY BUSINESSES

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Abstract

This research aims to improve the quality of service in the culinary business (Business "Ayam Krispi Athiyah") through the implementation of the Voice of Customer system. This research uses the comprehensive ADDIE development model. Data were collected through interviews, surveys, and online suggestion boxes based on barcodes. The research results show that the implementation of the Voice of Customer significantly improves customer satisfaction through quick responses to complaints, timely service, and consistent service quality. The online suggestion box barcode system facilitates real-time collection of customer feedback, supports data-driven decision-making, and provides opportunities for continuous improvement. Additionally, the application of the ADDIE model has proven effective in designing solutions that are relevant and aligned with customer needs. This study provides practical contributions for micro-enterprises to enhance competitiveness through customer-based service innovations.

Keywords : Business Development, Voice of Customer (VOC), Service Quality, ADDIE Model.

INTRODUCTION

In the ever-evolving business world, business development becomes the key to maintaining sustainability and enhancing competitiveness (Fadilla et al., 2023). A business does not only rely on current achievements, but must continuously innovate, adapt to market needs, and seize new opportunities. Business development is an activity that is consistently and continuously conducted with the aim of obtaining profit (Rakib et al., 2018). One of the strategic ways to achieve this is by implementing the Voice of Customer (VoC) system (Harto et al., 2023). Voice of Customer is the process of collecting and analyzing customer feedback to understand their needs, expectations, and preferences regarding the products and services offered by the company. Service quality is a special set of forms of production or service that can provide the ability to satisfy the needs and desires of the community. Another benefit of the voice of the customer is to be used in

improving service quality. Service quality must start from customer needs and end with customer perception (Putera et al., 2020). This shows that good service quality is not only viewed from the perspective of the service provider but also from the perspective of the customer. Meanwhile, customer perception of service quality is a comprehensive assessment of excellence (Adhilla, 2019). One of the SMEs currently undergoing business development, particularly in the aspect of improving service quality, is Ayam Krispi Athiyyah. Ayam Krispi Athiyyah is one of the businesses operating in the culinary field, specifically selling crispy chicken, located in Gowa Regency. Crispy chicken is a food that is currently popular among all segments of society, so business development is needed for the business to compete with other competitors. Improving service quality is currently a challenge faced by Ayam Krispi Athiyyah in their business development.

RESEARCH METHOD

This research was conducted from May to July 2024 at the Athiyyah crispy chicken business located in Gowa Regency. This research uses a descriptive quantitative and qualitative research approach with a development type of research using the Analysis, Design, Development, Implementation, and Evaluations (ADDIE) model. The focus of this research is the business development of Athiyyah crispy chicken through the voice of customer system. The description of the focus includes Reliability, Responsiveness, and Customer Satisfaction. This research aims to improve service quality. Research and Development is a research method for developing and testing products that will later be developed in the field of education (Amelina et al., 2024). This research uses the ADDIE development model. This development model was developed by Dick and Carry. ADDIE stands for Analysis, Design, Development or Production, Implementation or Delivery, and Evaluations. According to the steps of product development, this research and development model is more rational and more comprehensive than the 4D model. The core activities at each stage of development are also almost the same. Therefore, this model can be used for various forms of product development such as models, development strategies, and service quality. There are several development procedures regarding the research stages using the ADDIE development model:

1. Analysis

- a. Identifying the target audience and relevant customer segments.
- b. Conduct thorough research to understand the needs, desires, and problems faced by customers.
- c. Create customer profiles that include preferences, behaviors, and brand goals.

2. Design

- a. Create a framework or plan for collecting Voice Of Customer information, such as surveys, interviews, or data analysis.
- b. Determine the methods and tools that will be used to collect Voice Of Customer data.
- c. Create questions or topics to ensure relevant and useful information is obtained

from customers.

3. Development

- a. Create the tools or resources needed to collect Voice Of Customer data, such as survey forms, interview guidelines, or data analysis platforms.
- b. Test these tools or resources to ensure that they are effective in collecting the desired information.

4. Implementation

- a. Conducting Voice Of Customer data collection according to the plan that has been made.
- b. Ensure that the data collection methods are implemented well and consistently.
- c. Communicate with customers in a friendly and respectful manner to gain valuable insights.

5. Evaluation

- a. Analyze the results from the Voice Of Customer data collection to identify relevant patterns or trends.
- b. Compare the Voice Of Customer results with the existing product or service specifications, and identify the gaps between customer expectations and product performance.
- c. Use the information obtained to inform changes or improvements to existing products or services, or as input for the development of new products.

The subjects of this research trial use informants or individuals who are utilized to provide information about the situation and background conditions of the research. The subject of the research is the owner of the business "Ayam Krispi Athiyyah." Meanwhile, the respondents are 39 regular customers. The data collection techniques that can be used in this research are observation, interviews, questionnaires, and documentation. The data analysis technique used for data obtained from observations, interviews, and documentation is carried out by following steps such as data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions. Meanwhile, for data obtained from questionnaire instruments, it is analyzed using descriptive statistical analysis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research aims to understand how business development through the Voice of Customer (VOC) system can improve service quality at "Ayam Krispi Athiyyah." The VOC method is used to collect direct feedback from customers regarding their experiences with the provided services, thereby enabling the company to understand customer expectations and perceptions in depth.

1. Development of VOC-Based Business

The results of the VOC-based business development can improve the service quality at "Ayam Krispi Athiyyah." The results of the business development are outlined based on the following development stages.

Business Analysis. The service aspect has several weaknesses, such as untimeliness in service delivery and inadequate responses to customer needs. This issue affects

customers' perception of the overall quality of the business's services. Timeliness of service is one of the main factors that can affect customer satisfaction. The inability to meet the time expectations desired by customers can decrease their level of satisfaction. This is caused by the discomfort felt by customers due to longer wait times than expected. Therefore, it is important to identify and address service timeliness issues to enhance customer satisfaction. Based on previous research, customers who experience delays in service tend to feel less valued, which can ultimately reduce their loyalty to the brand (Mattila, 2004). This indicates that good time management is very influential in creating a positive customer experience. Therefore, businesses must pay attention to the aspect of timeliness in their daily operations. Timeliness in service can create a negative impression of the overall quality of service (Vu, 2021). If customers feel disappointed with the speed of service, they are more likely to provide negative feedback or even switch to competitors. Therefore, improving service efficiency should be the top priority for businesses to enhance customer experience.

Business Design Based on the VOC System. The design ensures that each data collection instrument can extract relevant information to understand and improve service aspects. The implementation of an online suggestion box has the main goal of providing an effective communication channel between customers and the company. With this system, customers can easily convey their suggestions, criticisms, or complaints anytime and anywhere. The use of online suggestion boxes has proven to increase customer participation in providing feedback. This is supported by the statement that online suggestion boxes can provide an effective communication channel between customers and the company (Garcia, 2021). With the ease of access and use, customers feel more valued because they can express their opinions directly at any time. This creates a better two-way relationship, where the company can hear and respond to customer needs more efficiently. Online suggestion boxes have the additional advantage of being able to collect data in real-time (Chen, 2022). The collected data can be analyzed to detect trends or patterns of recurring issues, allowing the company to take corrective actions promptly. Thus, the use of online suggestion boxes not only increases customer participation but also helps the company make more accurate data-driven decisions.

Business Development Based on the VOC System. In providing ease and efficiency in collecting customer feedback. QR barcodes are placed in strategic locations, such as dining tables, cashier areas, and store entrances. Customers simply need to scan the QR barcode using their devices, which will directly direct them to a digital form, such as Google Forms or a specialized application, to provide suggestions, complaints, or appreciation. QR barcode as a data collection tool has proven effective in increasing customer responses. The use of QR barcodes makes it easy for customers to access feedback forms without obstacles (Kumar et al., 2021). By simply scanning the QR code using a smartphone, customers can immediately share their opinions, making it easier to provide feedback. Thus, the QR barcode provides a double benefit: enhancing customer response and simplifying data analysis. **Implementation of Business Based on the VOC System.** By identifying certain patterns or trends that can serve as the basis for service improvements.

For example, the most frequently occurring complaints will be prioritized for handling first.

Researchers also use this data to make specific strategic recommendations, allowing businesses to implement changes that truly align with customer needs. Thus, the data collection process not only generates information but also serves as the initial step in creating a better customer experience. The use of customer feedback data can help businesses identify important areas for improvement. Analyzing feedback data allows companies to understand the issues frequently faced by customers and prioritize the necessary improvements (Davis, 2018). Through this approach, companies can respond to issues more quickly and efficiently, which in turn enhances customer satisfaction. The use of customer feedback can help companies better understand customer needs and adjust their services according to those expectations (Martin, 2017). By focusing on relevant feedback, companies can significantly enhance the customer experience and increase their loyalty. Therefore, collecting and utilizing customer feedback becomes key in service improvement.

Business Evaluation Based on the VOC System. Based on the evaluation results, the researchers formulated recommendations for improvement, such as increasing the efficiency of the ordering process, providing additional evaluations to business owners, or adding more staff during peak hours. Additionally, customer feedback is also used to establish new operational standards that better align with customer expectations. The evaluation stage is not only the end of the process but also the foundation for continuous improvement. Continuous evaluation allows companies to adapt to changing customer needs and market developments (S. Anderson, 2018). By regularly collecting and analyzing data, companies can continuously improve customer experience and maintain consistent service quality. This evaluation also serves as a tool to measure the success of the changes that have been made. This evaluation process not only assesses the success that has been achieved but also helps set new, more ambitious goals to improve service quality. Therefore, continuous evaluation becomes an important part of the service quality improvement strategy.

2. Level of Service Quality

The research results show that customer assessments of business development outcomes, viewed from the aspects of reliability, responsiveness, and customer satisfaction, fall into the high category.

Reliability. The "Ayam Krispi Athiyah" business is able to provide consistent, timely service that meets customer expectations. Based on the analysis, timeliness in service has become one of the main strengths, although some customers still feel their experience is less satisfactory, especially during peak hours. In addition, the accuracy of the service system is also a concern. Consistency in service is directly related to customer satisfaction. Customers tend to appreciate consistent and reliable service. When the service provided always meets customer expectations, they feel more satisfied and are more likely to return. When customers feel confident that they will always receive the same quality of service, they are more likely to choose that business repeatedly. This trust is the foundation of customer loyalty, which is crucial in creating long-term relationships.

Responsiveness. The ability of business owners to handle customer situations efficiently. providing a special evaluation to business owners regarding problem-solving techniques and empathy towards customers. With this approach, the business can ensure that customers feel heard and prioritized. Responsive service enhances the positive perception of the business. When staff can provide quick and effective responses to customer problems or questions, it increases their satisfaction (Garcia, 2021). Quick and efficient service also shows that the company cares about customer needs, which enhances the positive image of the business. When customers feel valued and appreciated, they are more likely to continue interacting with the company. This also increases customer loyalty and reduces the likelihood of them switching to competitors, adding that a quick response to customer complaints or requests. The company has an efficient and reliable system (Brown & Lee, 2022). Responsive service is the main indicator of the quality of the services provided, and this is very important in maintaining sustainable customer satisfaction. Customer Satisfaction. The "Ayam Krispi Athiyyah" business can enhance customer satisfaction by utilizing feedback data from the online suggestion box to continuously monitor and evaluate its services. With continuous improvements based on customer feedback, the business will not only meet customer expectations but also build long-term beneficial relationships with them. The use of customer feedback can lead to long-term satisfaction improvements. When companies actively listen to and respond to customer feedback, it creates a sense of appreciation that enhances their satisfaction (C. Anderson & Smith, 2020). Customers who feel heard are more likely to remain loyal to the brand and recommend products or services to others (Azzahrah et al., 2023). This leads to increased customer satisfaction because they feel they have a role in improving service quality. The feedback received is not only used for improvements but also gives customers a sense of contribution to the business's development. Satisfied customers tend to provide positive feedback that can enhance the business's reputation (Kim, 2022). Therefore, effectively utilizing feedback can create long-term relationships with customers, which in turn enhances their satisfaction and loyalty towards the company.

CONCLUSION

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that:

1. the Voice of Customer system effectively helps Ayam Krispi Athiyyah to identify customer needs and expectations. This allows the business to improve its response to customer complaints and preferences,
2. Through the implementation of the ADDIE development model, the business successfully enhanced important aspects of service quality, such as reliability, responsiveness, and customer satisfaction, and
3. The implementation of the Voice of Customer system contributes to the improvement of service quality, ultimately creating customer satisfaction and loyalty, which supports overall business growth. Conducting formal customer satisfaction surveys to obtain more structured and in-depth feedback regarding the products and services offered. This research is expected to serve as a

reference and study, as well as a basis for further studies related to the same issues, thereby strengthening the results of this research.

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